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Estimating Calibration Needs of Weighing Equipment and Customer Segmentation in Industrial Facilities

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Abstract

Weighing equipment plays an essential role in industries but can become unreliable without regular calibration. Although the errors of these equipment are usually unnoticeable, they can gradually cause considerable losses to industries. Furthermore, due to the variety of customers using weighing equipment, their classification can cause a better understanding of their preferences and help businesses apply effective strategies. In this study, using the findings of previous studies and experts' opinions, criteria to measure the calibration importance were extracted using the fuzzy Delphi method. Data was obtained from the CRM of Pand Industrial Group and clustering was performed using the K-MEANS method. Next, the weights of the criteria were determined using Shannon's method and

Chen and Huang's fuzzification method. Then, the calibration importance ranking was obtained for each cluster using TOPSIS, SAW, VIKOR, and ELECTRE methods, and suggestions were made regarding the optimal number of calibrations per year.

Keywords: Calibration; Customer Segmentation; Weighing Equipment; Industrial Facilities; CRM (Customer Relationship Management); Multi-Criteria Decision Making (MCDM).

1. Introduction

Quality control is one of the paramount stages in modern industries' production processes. Measurement is virtually ubiquitous in today's industrial landscape, with measurements being taken at nearly every stage of production. Measurement and control methodologies offer an opportunity to establish specific requirements under which a company can produce high-quality products and meet consumer demands. Accurate measurements not only instil confidence but also prove to be efficient in terms of time and cost savings [1]. Over the past three decades, and following the digitization of scales and weighbridges utilized in industries, the precision and accuracy of these instruments have consistently been subjects of discussion and scrutiny. Undoubtedly, the weighing industry stands as one of the most impactful factors in industrial profitability. Given the paramount importance of high-quality products and competitively priced services in today's global markets, companies must not only focus on sourcing raw materials and products but also rely on calibration service providers. Calibration of measurement devices is indeed a prerequisite stipulated by the ISO 9001 standard for quality [2].

Calibration of measurement equipment stands as one of the most critical processes employed to maintain the accuracy of instruments. Calibration is the process of verifying the accuracy of measurement equipment to provide acceptable results. It serves to eliminate or minimize factors that introduce errors in measurements. The primary objective of calibration is to minimize any measurement errors and deliver the highest

level of precision in measurement equipment, ensuring that measurement instruments depict an accurate and reliable representation of the measured quantity. Calibration methods are applied to industrial devices to ensure the accuracy and consistency of measured values [1]

Sensor errors in weighing equipment incur annual costs in the millions of dollars for industries, including the mining sector. Unlike glaring and substantial errors, "calibration errors" often go unnoticed, accumulate over time, and are challenging to detect. Even minor errors can lead to economic losses that compound over time [3]. The absence of calibration in weighing equipment across various scales can introduce significant additional costs and hidden losses to businesses. If the raw materials and final products of these units hold high prices and values, as is the case with refinery and mining products, the financial losses due to the lack of calibration in weighing equipment become irreparable.

On the other hand, considering the diversity of industries that utilize weighing equipment, it is imperative to pay attention to customer segmentation. Market segmentation is a strategy that allows a business or industry to analyse the market structure by dividing a broad consumer base into homogeneous groups. With proper market segmentation, service operators can plan effective marketing strategies to cater to their primary target audience [4]. Nowadays, customers use digital media to seek solutions to their problems, and companies must be attentive to this trend in a timely manner. By analysing relevant information and utilizing statistical data, companies can create awareness and loyalty, attracting new customers based on their specific needs and circumstances [5]. In today's world, organizations are actively seeking diverse strategies to expand access and loyalty to their customers. Statistics show that effective customer engagement has a positive impact on a company's profits. The field of Customer

Relationship Management (CRM) has seen significant growth, advancement, and maturity over the past decade [6]. Customers are the primary assets for a company's sustainability, and effective customer management profoundly affects a company's revenue. Customers are the determinants of an organization's success or failure, and undoubtedly, without customers, establishing a business is virtually impossible. Beyond acquiring new customers, maintaining and retaining existing ones is crucial. There is no shortage of companies that lose a significant number of customers due to inadequate service. Customer segmentation is one of the methods that can be employed to support companies' strategic needs in improving and developing customer relationships [7].

In identifying business customers, customer segmentation can lead to a better understanding of the behaviour and preferences of different customer groups, helping businesses formulate effective strategies for each customer segment. Customer segmentation is the process of identifying customers who share common characteristics and grouping them accordingly [8]. Companies should initially identify the characteristics, needs, preferences, perspectives, and opinions of their customers regarding the services or products offered. Therefore, existing data can be leveraged to develop effective segmentation solutions [9].

In recent years, Business-to-Business (B2B) marketers have experimented with a wide spectrum of communication and marketing tools in their efforts to address challenges and ambitious goals and to achieve performance objectives [10]. However, these changes and experiments are not sufficient, even if they come with increased responsiveness to customer demands for greater collaboration [11]. Based on this, B2B marketers have shown their willingness to go beyond simple advertising and engage more effectively with customers [12]. To this end, accruing customer attention should be

accompanied by a proper understanding and planning to achieve goals and provide services to customers.

Based on the information provided, it is crucial to give special attention to the calibration of weighing equipment to reduce errors and potential losses. Additionally, considering customer segmentation, companies providing calibration and repair services should plan appropriately and at the right time to position themselves within the view of their customers. To date, various techniques have been employed in research to optimize calibration [13];[14], improve calibration rates [15], choose calibration service providers [16], and perform customer segmentation using heuristic algorithms [4,7,9,17-19]. However, none of these studies have explicitly sought to segment customers for estimating the optimal number of calibrations, particularly in the context of weighing equipment. Consequently, this research aims to achieve suitable customer segmentation based on criteria established for the significance of calibration. Subsequently, employing decision-making methods, it intends to estimate the importance of calibration for weighing equipment within each of these segments and provide recommendations for the optimal number of calibrations.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Calibration

Calibration means comparing a measuring device with a standard and obtaining the error rate of this device compared to it, and if necessary, readjusting the device with the relevant standards. In simpler words, it is the calibration of the measurement and the accuracy of the measuring device compared to a source and approved reference. In fact, calibration determines the efficiency characteristics of the device or reference materials by making

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direct comparisons. Every device that is used for measurement and mentioned in the implementation methods needs to determine the accuracy and precision or calibration [2]. Another definition is provided in ISO 10012 and it explains calibration as follows: "A set of operations that are established under specified conditions and specifies the relationship between the values indicated by the measuring instrument and the corresponding values of that quantity by the reference standard. [13]. The following are the main goals of calibration: In order to ensure that the items are read from the device, to determine the correctness of the values read from the device, Due to establishment of device traceability to reference standards. Traceability is actually the most important feature that is a measurement; The existence of this feature makes it possible to track and compare the results with national and then international standards [14].

Kim & Kim (2021) use three statistical methods for Water Quality Data to Improve Water Quality Calibration and Validation. The statistical method proposed in this study can be used when it is not long or enough to observe the water quality [13].

In a study, Bhar, Kumar, Qi & Malone (2020) have investigated the coordination of well-calibrated agricultural system model and optimal input management. Well-calibrated agricultural system model with many parameters is critical for optimized agriculture management and decision making. Once calibrated, fertilization and irrigation decisions were optimized so that farm profit is maximized. These methods increased the yield by 7% and profit by 10% as compared to what was applied in the field [14].

Prabandanu and Ikatrinasari (2020) studied the decision making about the calibration rate of telecommunication devices. They found that the exact method used in compiling telecommunication equipment calibration rates is the activity-based costing method [15].

Toklu (2018) has conducted a study with the fuzzy TOPSIS method for the problem of

selecting a calibration supplier in an automobile company. This study includes a model for selecting the most suitable calibration supplier using a fuzzy technique for order performance with the method of similarity to the ideal solution (TOPSIS). In this study, a case study approach for the calibration of a torque limiter wrench in an automotive company is presented [16].

2.2. Customer Segmentation

In recent years, the competition between companies in maintenance in this field has increased significantly. Company profits can be improved with a customer segmentation model. Customer retention is more important than attracting new customers. According to the Pareto principle, 20 percent of customers contribute more to the company's revenue than the rest [20]. Customer segmentation can be done using a variety of unique customer characteristics to help business people customize marketing plans, identify trends, plan product development and advertising campaigns, and offer relevant products. provide Customer segmentation personalizes people's messages to better connect with target groups. The most common attributes used in customer segmentation are location, age, gender, income, lifestyle, and previous purchase behaviour [21]. When segmenting customers, it is assumed that all customers are not equal and the market is not homogeneous. This method creates groups of customers that are similar in some ways in each customer group. When customer segmentation becomes necessary, a mass market strategy has little chance of success in a competitive market. Also, by identifying and classifying different segments of customers, targeting of potential customers and related forecasts can be achieved effectively [22].

In a study, Choi, Choi, Yoon & Joung (2020) have investigated the understanding of customers based on the characteristics of customer selection and segmentation [4]. In a

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study, Hartini, Gata, Kurniawan, Setiawan and Novel (2020) studied the segmentation of cosmetics and health care customers in Indonesia using clustering algorithm [7].

Maulina, Surjandari & Rus (2019) have used a data mining approach to segment B2B customers. In this paper, different clustering algorithms, especially centre-based clustering, K-Means, CLARA and PAM are compared with C-Means fuzzy clustering [9]. The aim of this research is to find the optimal number of clusters using the clustering algorithm with the best reliability score. Among the three clustering methods, K-Means has the best reliability score.

Kuo & Zulvia (2018) have used an improved artificial bee colony optimization algorithm for customer segmentation. This study proposes a new automatic clustering algorithm using a combination of artificial bee colony optimization algorithm and K-means algorithm (iABC) [19].

An et al. (2018) in their study proposed a new approach for customer segmentation using online customer data for products distributed through online social media platforms. The results show that this approach can identify both behavioural and demographic segments of the customer using real online customer data from which personas representing real groups of people can be generated [18].

Hwang, Jung & Suh (2004) have proposed an LTV model to segment customers based on customer value. This study states that since the early 1980s, the concept of relationship management gained importance in the field of marketing. In this paper, an LTV model is proposed by considering past profit share, potential profit and customer defection probability [23]. A framework for analysing customer value and segmenting customers based on their value is also covered.

As stated, there are gaps in researches regarding equipment calibration, and despite the high importance of calibration in industries and its direct effect on business profitability, only limited researches have been conducted in this regard, and this research gap is related to weighing equipment and industry. The weight is very prominent.

Also, by examining the research conducted in the field of equipment calibration, it was clearly observed that research on the calibration of weighing equipment has not been comprehensively conducted so far, and there is a research gap to optimize the number of calibrations of weighing equipment based on effective criteria on vacuum calibration. The researches carried out so far have used various techniques to optimize calibration, improve calibration rate, choose calibration service providers and segment customers, but none of these researches have specifically sought segmentation of customers to estimate the optimal number of calibrations, and this case is about equipment. Weighing has not been done either. For this purpose, in this research, we will look for the appropriate segmentation of customers based on the obtained criteria for the importance of calibration, and then, with decision-making methods, we will estimate the importance of calibration of weighing equipment for each of these clusters and suggest the optimal number of calibrations.

3. Research Methodology

The present study was conducted as applied research using a quantitative approach and a correlation method.

The statistical population of the research encompasses all customers in the weighing industry of Iran within the CRM of the "Pand" industrial group, totalling over 30,000 individuals. The sample size for this study, determined using the Morgan-Krejcie method with a 5% margin of error, is a minimum of 379 cases.

The research implementation stages is as follows:

- **Step One:** Extraction of appropriate calibration importance criteria through a review of the literature and expert-proposed criteria.
- **Step Two:** Determination of final criteria using the fuzzy Delphi method.
- **Step Three:** Extraction of data and industries purchasing weighing scales and truck scales from the CRM of the "Pand" industrial group based on the obtained criteria.
- **Step Four:** Customer clustering using the K-means method.
- **Step Five:** Weight determination of criteria twice, first using the Shannon entropy method and then based on expert opinions, and fuzzy conversion of numbers in accordance with a seven-point spectrum to obtain the final weights.
- **Step Six:** Scoring and determining the importance of calibration for each cluster using TOPSIS, SAW, VIKOR, and ELECTRE methods.
- **Step Seven:** Analysis of the results obtained from customer segmentation and the importance of calibration in their respective industries.

The necessary criteria for clustering are initially selected by considering the criteria obtained from the literature review and expert-proposed criteria using the fuzzy Delphi technique. Subsequently, using the CRM of the "Pand" industrial group, the required data are extracted based on the specified criteria as outlined in Table 1.

Table 1. Research data collection tools

#	Tool/Type	Criteria for Use
1	Determining the types of industries purchasing scales	Customer segmentation
2	Number of calibrations performed by the customer per year for scales	To estimate the number of calibrations
3	Determining the types of industries purchasing truck scales	Customer segmentation

4	Number of calibrations performed by the customer per year for truck scales	To estimate the number of calibrations
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Next, clustering of customers was performed using the K-means clustering method with SPSS Modeler software. In this context, K defines the predetermined number of clusters to be created in this process, where $K = 2$ signifies two clusters, and $K = 3$ implies three clusters, and so on. K-Means is an iterative algorithm that partitions an unlabelled dataset into K distinct clusters, each containing data points with similar features. This approach allows us to group data into different clusters, revealing distinct categories within the dataset. This method provides a suitable way to discover groupings in unlabelled datasets without the need for any prior training. This is a centroid-based algorithm in which each cluster is associated with a centre point. The main objective of this algorithm is to minimize the total distances between data points and their respective clusters. The K-Means algorithm takes an unlabelled dataset as input, divides the dataset into K clusters, and iteratively refines the process until it finds the best clusters. The value of K must be predetermined in this algorithm. The K-Means clustering algorithm operates as follows:

Utilizing an iterative process, it determines the optimal values for centroids. Each data point is assigned to its nearest centroid among the k centroids. Data points that are close to the k centroids form clusters. Therefore, each cluster consists of data points sharing some common characteristics and is distant from other clusters [24]. In this study, clustering was performed using the k-means method, ranging from 2 clusters to 20 clusters, and the silhouette score was computed each time. According to the silhouette score, which measures the proximity of data points within a cluster and their distance from neighboring clusters, a value close to 1 implies that the datum is appropriately

placed within a cluster, while a value close to -1 indicates that the datum has been misclassified into the wrong cluster.

Additionally, once, the obtained criteria were weighted using the Shannon entropy method [25]. Another time, criteria were weighted using the Chen-Hwang fuzzy method based on expert opinions. Ultimately, the final weights for each of the criteria were determined.

Finally, the importance of calibration for each cluster was measured using four methods: TOPSIS, SAW, VIKOR, and ELECTRE, along with the existing criteria. The final ranking was presented using an averaging method of the results from these four methods.

4. Results

4.1. Results of the Delphi Technique

Out of the criteria extracted from previous articles and the criteria proposed by experts, 15 final criteria were selected for assessment. A Delphi questionnaire, using a 5-point Likert scale, was administered to the experts. After experts completed the questionnaire, the criteria were evaluated through the Delphi method, and ultimately, 7 criteria were selected as the final criteria.

Table 2. Evaluation of criteria based on the Delphi technique

Criteria	Exp 1	Exp 2	Exp 3	Exp 4	Exp 5	Exp 6	Exp 7	1	m	u	D-Value	Final State
Equipment Type	1	5	4	4	4	4	4	1	3.38762796	5	3.25841864	Dis
Data Trends Obtained from Previous Calibrations	1	4	5	4	3	3	4	1	3.120318506	5	3.080212337	Dis
Equipment Maintenance and Repair Records	2	3	3	5	5	3	2	2	3.091682043	5	3.227788028	Dis

Equipment Frequency of (Weighing Use Frequency)	5	5	5	5	5	5	4	4	4.8431254 3	5	4.728750286	App
Degree of Equipment Susceptibility to Wear Tear	2	5	4	3	4	4	4	2	3.5896458 43	5	3.559763895	Dis
Frequency of Equipment Inspections	1	4	5	4	4	5	4	1	3.4973572 43	5	3.331571495	Dis
Frequency of Equipment Cross-Tests	3	2	5	4	3	4	5	2	3.5567021 67	5	3.537801444	Dis
Changes in Environmental Conditions (Temperature, Humidity, etc.)	3	5	4	5	5	4	5	3	4.3610267 51	5	4.240684501	App
Desired Measurement Accuracy	2	4	5	4	3	5	4	2	3.7059187 24	5	3.63727915	Dis
Weighing Platforms Material	4	4	5	4	4	5	5	4	4.4014204 21	5	4.43428028	App
Type of Load Cell	4	5	5	5	4	5	4	4	4.5439876 42	5	4.529325095	App
Truck Scale Capacity (Tonnage)	3	5	5	4	5	5	5	3	4.5022855 74	5	4.334857049	App
Weighted Material Value	4	5	5	4	4	4	5	4	4.4014204 21	5	4.43428028	App
Location of Truck Scale Installation (Outdoor or Indoor setting)	5	5	5	4	5	5	5	4	4.8431254 3	5	4.728750286	App
Business Category (Material Procurement or Sales)	3	4	4	4	3	4	4	3	3.6843697 63	4	3.622913175	Dis

58.68667594

Threshold	3.912445063
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Note: Exp: Expert, D-Value: Defuzzied Value, Dis: Dismissed, App: Approved

4.2. Data Extraction and Identifying Industries Using Scales and Truck Scales from Pand Industrial Group CRM Based on Derived Criteria

The required data were obtained from Pand industrial group CRM based on these 7 criteria. The dataset comprised 5,697 cases, with fields including scale tonnage (truck, trailer, dump truck), daily weighing frequency (1-5 times a day, more than 6 times a day), weighted material value, scale material (concrete/metal), load cell type (Chinese,

European, German), scale installation location (indoor/outdoor), and environmental condition changes for each data point, categorized into 10 specific industries (food industries, metal industries, mining, oil, gas and petrochemical industries, livestock and poultry farming, horticulture and agriculture, manufacturing plants, construction and civil engineering, customs, general-purpose truck scales).

4.3. K-Means Clustering Results

In this stage, data points need to be clustered. Clustering was performed using the K-Means method with the assistance of data mining software, SPSS Modeler.

Based on Figure 1, in the 7-cluster configuration, the silhouette score was the highest at 0.59, whereas in the other clustering numbers, scores lower than 0.5 were recorded.

Figure 1: Clustering results using the K-means algorithm

After clustering, the following clusters were identified:

4.3.1. Cluster 1: Economic Truck Scales

Number of data points (934), average weighted material value (2.46 out of 3), number of

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weightings per day (1-5 times), scale tonnage (truck scale, 1.74 out of 3), truck scale material type (concrete, 1 out of 2), major load cell type (Chinese, 2.31 out of 3) environmental conditions changes (moderate, 1.81 out of 3), truck scale installation location (indoor area 1 out of 2).

4.3.2. Cluster 2: Control Truck Scales

Number of data points (276), average weighted material value (1 out of 3), number of weightings per day (>6 times), scale tonnage (truck scale, 1.89 out of 3), truck scale material type (metal, 1.67 out of 2), major load cell type (German, 1.37 out of 3) environmental conditions changes (moderate, 2 out of 3), truck scale installation location (outdoor area 1.99 out of 2).

4.3.3. Cluster 3: High-Value Truck Scales

Number of data points (1106), average weighted material value (2.67 out of 3), number of weightings per day (1-5 times), scale tonnage (truck scale, 1.65 out of 3), truck scale material type (metal, 2 out of 2), major load cell type (German, 1.54 out of 3) environmental conditions changes (moderate, 1.89 out of 3), truck scale installation location (outdoor area 2 out of 2).

4.3.4. Cluster 4: Field Truck Scales

Number of data points (1034), average weighted material value (2.59 out of 3), number of weightings per day (1-5 times), scale tonnage (truck scale, 1.74 out of 3), truck scale material type (concrete, 1 out of 2), major load cell type (European, 1.94 out of 3) environmental conditions changes (high, 2.11 out of 3), truck scale installation location (outdoor area 2 out of 2).

4.3.5. Cluster 5: Roadside Truck Scales

Number of data points (308), average weighted material value (1 out of 3), number of weightings per day (>6 times), scale tonnage (truck scale 1.57 out of 3), truck scale material type (concrete, 1 out of 2), major load cell type (Chinese, 2.83 out of 3) environmental conditions changes (moderate, 2 out of 3), truck scale installation location (outdoor area 1.98 out of 2).

4.3.6. Cluster 6: General Purpose Truck Scales

Number of data points (1146), average weighted material value (2.16 out of 3), number of weightings per day (1-5 times), scale tonnage (truck scale, 1.33 out of 3), truck scale material type (concrete, 1.07 out of 2), major load cell type (Chinese, 2.89 out of 3) environmental conditions changes (low, 1.09 out of 3), truck scale installation location (outdoor area 2 out of 2).

4.3.7. Cluster 7: Business Truck Scales

Number of data points (892), average weighted material value (2.39 out of 3), number of weightings per day (1-5 times), scale tonnage (truck scale, 1.77 out of 3), truck scale material type (metal, 1.07 out of 2), major load cell type (Chinese, 1.36 out of 3) environmental conditions changes (moderate, 1.09 out of 3), truck scale installation location (indoor area 1 out of 2). Figure 2 illustrates the overall results of the K-means method.

Figure 2. Summary of the model and cluster quality

4.4. Determining the Weight of Criteria

4.4.1. Determining the Weight of Criteria Based on Shannon method

Subsequently, the average values obtained from K-means for each criterion and cluster were assigned weights using the Shannon method. Initially, the average values obtained for each cluster are specified in Table 3.

Table 3. Weight assignment of values obtained for criteria and clusters

	Number Of Weightings Per Day	Load Cell Type	Truck Scale Tonnage	Weighted Material Value	Truck Scale Material Type	Truck Scale Installation Location	Environmental Conditions Changes
Cluster 1	1.00	2.31	1.74	2.46	1.00	1.00	1.81
Cluster 2	2.00	1.37	1.89	1.00	1.67	1.99	2.00
Cluster 3	1.00	1.54	1.65	2.67	2.00	2.00	1.89
Cluster 4	1.00	1.94	1.74	2.59	1.00	2.00	2.11
Cluster 5	2.00	2.83	1.57	1.00	1.00	1.98	2.00
Cluster 6	1.00	2.89	1.33	2.16	1.07	2.00	1.09
Cluster 7	1.00	1.36	1.77	2.39	2.00	1.00	1.57
Sum	9.00	14.24	11.69	14.27	9.74	11.97	12.47

The confidence level and uncertainty level for each of the criteria were calculated. Finally, the weight of each criterion was computed using the Shannon method. The results of this stage are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Calculating the uncertainty level

Calculating the Uncertainty Level								
	Number Of Weightings Per Day	Load Cell Type	Truck Scale Tonnage	Weighted Material Value	Truck Scale Material Type	Truck Scale Installation Location	Environmental Conditions Changes	
	0.970835763	0.977169621	0.997356569	0.968187713	0.974464671	0.980295106	0.9906492	
Calculating the Confidence Level								
	Number Of Weightings Per Day	Load Cell Type	Truck Scale Tonnage	Weighted Material Value	Truck Scale Material Type	Truck Scale Installation Location	Environmental Conditions Changes	Sum
	0.029164237	0.022830379	0.002643431	0.031812287	0.025535329	0.019704894	0.0093508	0.141041357
Calculating the Criteria Weight (Wi)								
W	Number Of Weightings Per Day	Load Cell Type	Truck Scale Tonnage	Weighted Material Value	Truck Scale Material Type	Truck Scale Installation Location	Environmental Conditions Changes	
	0.206777911	0.1618701	0.01874224	0.225552902	0.181048519	0.139710043	0.066298285	

4.4.2. Determining the Weight of Criteria Based on Expert Opinions

In this stage, a questionnaire was administered to experts to determine the weight of the criteria. The experts provided scores for each criterion using a 7-point Likert scale, and these scores were subsequently transformed into fuzzy numbers corresponding to the 7-point scale [26]. Then, the average of the fuzzy numbers was calculated, followed by defuzzification, normalization, and obtaining the weight of each criterion based on expert opinions in a fuzzy manner [27].

The scores provided by the 7 experts for determining the weight of each criterion is provided in Table 5.

Table 5. Determining the weight of criteria based on expert opinions

	Number Of Weightings Per Day	Load Cell Type	Truck Scale Tonnage	Weighted Material Value	Truck Scale Material Type	Truck Scale Installation Location	Environmental Conditions Changes
Expert 1	7	6	7	4	6	6	4
Expert 2	7	7	7	2	4	7	2
Expert 3	7	7	7	1	4	4	3
Expert 4	6	7	6	3	3	6	2
Expert 5	5	7	6	1	4	7	4
Expert 6	6	7	7	3	3	5	1
Expert 7	7	7	7	2	4	6	3

Expert ratings were transformed into fuzzy numbers corresponding to the 7-point Likert scale. Subsequently, using the Chen and Hwang method, the weights of each criterion were calculated based on expert opinions. The fuzzy numbers were normalized, and then crisp values were obtained. Finally, the average weight for each criterion was calculated to determine the final weights (Table 6).

Table 6. Calculation of crisp numbers and averages for each criterion

Step04: Calculation of Crisp Value							
	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7
A1	0.96	0.84	0.96	0.53	0.84	0.84	0.53
A2	0.95	0.95	0.95	0.17	0.50	0.95	0.17
A3	0.95	0.95	0.95	0.05	0.50	0.50	0.33
A4	0.83	0.95	0.83	0.33	0.33	0.83	0.17
A5	0.67	0.95	0.83	0.05	0.50	0.95	0.50
A6	0.32	0.43	0.35	0.37	0.33	0.67	0.05
A7	0.32	0.43	0.35	0.37	0.50	0.83	0.33

AVG	0.71	0.79	0.75	0.27	0.50	0.80	0.30
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Sum
4.11

In the end, the weight of each criterion based on expert opinions (λ_i) was calculated by dividing the average of each criterion by the sum of the averages, as shown in Table 7.

Table 7. Determining the weight of criteria based on expert opinions

Determining the weight of criteria based on expert opinions (λ_i)							
λ	Number Of Weightings Per Day	Load Cell Type	Truck Scale Tonnage	Weighted Material Value	Truck Scale Material Type	Truck Scale Installation Location	Environmental Conditions Changes
	0.173742 46861501 5	0.19159 6326449 994	0.18176 869271 502	0.064798 3472676 418	0.121854 53810526 2	0.19373114 1362944	0.0725084 854841231

4.4.3. Determining the Weight of Criteria Based on Shannon method

The final weight of each criterion was determined using the formula $Q_i = \frac{W_i * \lambda_i}{\sum W_i \lambda_i}$, and the results and final weights of each criterion are presented in Table 8.

Here, W_i represents the results of K-means clustering, λ_i represents the results of expert opinions based on the Chen-Hwang method.

Table 8. Final weights of criteria

	Number Of Weightings Per Day	Load Cell Type	Truck Scale Tonnage	Weighted Material Value	Truck Scale Material Type	Truck Scale Installation Location	Environmental Conditions Changes
W_i	0.2067779 11	0.161 8701	0.0187 4224	0.22555 2902	0.181048 519	0.1397100 43	0.06629828 5
λ_i	0.1737424 69	0.191 5963 26	0.1817 68693	0.06479 8347	0.121854 538	0.1937311 41	0.07250848 5
$\frac{W_i}{\lambda_i}$	0.0359261 05	0.031 0137 16	0.0034 06752	0.01461 5455	0.022061 584	0.0270661 86	0.00480718 8
$\sum W_i \lambda_i = 0.1388$ 96987							
Q_i	0.2586528 73	0.223 2857 4	0.0245 27187	0.10522 5143	0.158834 142	0.1948651 78	0.03460973 7

4.5. Determining the Weight of Criteria

In the final section, using the criteria weights and the averages obtained from K-means for each cluster, the importance of calibration for each cluster was determined using the TOPSIS, SAW, VIKOR, and ELECTRE methods. The final weight of each criterion is depicted in Table 9.

Table 9. The final weights of criteria

Criteria	Criteria weight
C1	0.258652873
C2	0.22328574
C3	0.024527187
C4	0.105225143
C5	0.158834142
C6	0.194865178
C7	0.034609737

The decision matrix based on the averages obtained from the K-means method for each cluster and criterion is presented in Table 10.

Table 10. Decision matrix

Decision Matrix	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7
Cluster 1	1	2.31	1.74	2.46	1	1	1.81
Cluster 2	2	1.37	1.89	1	1.67	1.99	2
Cluster 3	1	1.54	1.65	2.67	2	2	1.89
Cluster 4	1	1.94	1.74	2.59	1	2	2.11
Cluster 5	2	2.83	1.57	1	1	1.98	2
Cluster 6	1	2.89	1.33	2.16	1.07	2	1.09
Cluster 7	1	1.36	1.77	2.39	2	1	1.57

Using the averaging method, the rankings obtained from the 4 ranking methods were averaged to calculate the final ranking of calibration importance for each cluster, as shown in Table 11.

Table 11. The final ranking of calibration importance for each cluster

	ELECTRE	VIKOR	SAW	TOPSIS	OVERALL
Cluster 1	6	7	7	6	6
Cluster 2	4	2	2	2	2

Cluster 3	3	3	3	4	3
Cluster 4	5	5	5	5	5
Cluster 5	1	1	1	1	1
Cluster 6	2	4	4	3	3
Cluster 7	7	6	6	7	6

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, weighing equipment exerts a direct influence on various industries, and the reliability of such equipment remains compromised in the absence of standards and calibration. Errors occurring within weighing instruments during the weighing process often go unnoticed, yet these minor inaccuracies can lead to significant long-term losses for industries and businesses. On the other hand, considering the diverse range of industries utilizing weighing equipment, attention must be paid to customer segmentation. Identifying and categorizing customers in business can lead to a better understanding of the behaviours and preferences of different customer groups, thereby assisting businesses in formulating effective strategies tailored to each customer segment.

To this end, this research aims to segment customers based on the number of calibrations required annually for weighing equipment used in industrial units. This segmentation will enable calibration service providers to more effectively access their target market and customers. Additionally, industrial units equipped with weighing instruments will have a specific framework for calibrating their equipment based on the industry in which they operate.

After conducting calculations using the mentioned methods and processes, Table 11 was generated. This table presents the final results of ranking the importance of calibration for each cluster based on the clustering findings. The results of the clustering are explained as follows:

Cluster 1, referred to as "Economic Truck Scales," comprises truck scales with an 80-ton capacity. They have concrete weighing platforms, use Chinese load cells, perform 1-5 weightings per day, are installed in an indoor setting, and experience moderate environmental changes in the area where these truck scales are installed.

Industries represented in this cluster include manufacturing factories, food industries, oil and gas, petrochemicals, livestock farming, and poultry farming, as well as metal industries.

Cluster 2, referred to as "Control Truck Scales," consists of truck scales with an 80-ton capacity. These scales have metal weighing platforms and utilize German load cells. They perform more than 6 weightings per day, are installed in an outdoor setting, and experience moderate environmental changes in the area where they are installed. Representatives in this cluster include customs authorities and general-purpose truck scales.

Cluster 3, referred to as "High-Value Truck Scales," comprises truck scales with a 50-ton capacity. These scales have metal weighing platforms and utilize German load cells. They perform 1-5 weightings per day, are installed in an outdoor setting, and experience moderate environmental changes in the area where they are installed. These truck scales are used for weighing materials that hold significant value for businesses, such as metal ores, minerals, chemicals, and iron products, among others.

Industries represented in this cluster include metal industries, construction and civil engineering, mining, oil and gas, petrochemicals, manufacturing factories, food industries, livestock farming, poultry farming, agriculture, and horticulture.

Cluster 4, denoted as "Field Truck Scales," consists of truck scales with an 80-ton capacity. These scales have concrete weighing platforms and use European load cells. They perform 1-5 weightings per day, are installed in an outdoor setting, and experience

high environmental variability in the region where they are installed. These scales are primarily used for weighing materials of high value.

Industries in this cluster are predominantly represented by construction and civil engineering, as well as metal industries.

Cluster 5, designated as "Roadside Truck Scales," includes truck scales with an 80-ton capacity. These scales have metal weighing platforms and utilize Chinese load cells. They perform more than 6 weightings per day, are installed in an outdoor setting, and experience moderate environmental changes in the region where they are installed.

Representatives in this cluster include general-purpose truck scales and customs authorities.

Cluster 6, referred to as "General-Purpose Truck Scales," consists of truck scales with a 50-ton capacity. These scales have concrete weighing platforms and use Chinese load cells. They perform 1-5 weightings per day, are installed in an outdoor setting, and experience minimal environmental changes in the region where they are installed.

The primary representatives in this cluster include livestock farming, poultry farming, agriculture, and horticulture industries.

Cluster 7, named "Business Truck Scales," comprises truck scales with an 80-ton capacity. These scales have metal weighing platforms and utilize Chinese load cells. They perform 1-5 weightings per day, are installed in an indoor setting, and experience moderate environmental changes in the region where they are installed.

The predominant representatives in this cluster are the food industry and manufacturing factories.

As logically anticipated, the rankings have decisively identified Cluster 5, or the "Roadside Truck Scales," as the category with the highest need for calibration throughout

the year, and the importance of calibration for this cluster surpasses that of any other cluster.

Given the high frequency of weightings throughout the day, the substantial 80-ton capacity of these truck scales, the use of cost-effective Chinese load cells with low credibility compared to other market brands, and their installation in uncovered outdoor locations with a high risk of foreign material debris falling onto the scales, and the heavy vehicles stopping on them, the importance of regular and more frequent calibration throughout the year for Cluster 5 surpasses that of other clusters. In the next ranking, Control truck Scales are positioned, sharing a similar situation with the previous cluster. These scales are primarily utilized in customs facilities, with the distinction of using German load cells, which enjoy higher credibility and cost within the load cell market. Given the critical role these scales play as control points in border customs and roadside locations, the importance of more frequent calibration throughout the year for this cluster also exceeds that of other clusters.

Next in importance, calibration throughout the year is crucial for both "High-Value Truck Scales" and "General-Purpose Truck Scales." High-Value Truck Scales must establish a specific calibration plan due to the high value of the materials weighed, as even minor errors in the weighing process can result in significant losses given the high value of the materials involved in their transactions.

General-Purpose Scales, too, merit calibration consideration within this cluster. Given the use of Chinese load cells, which are known to possess lower credibility and pricing compared to other brands available in the market, and considering the installation of these scales in exposed outdoor environments where the risk of foreign material contamination is considerably high, calibration holds significance for this cluster as well.

Field Truck Scales are ranked next in importance. These scales are typically installed in outdoor, uncovered spaces and are primarily used in construction and civil engineering industries where the natural occurrence of foreign materials such as soil, sand, and gravel are common. Environmental conditions in the locations where these truck scales are installed are characterized by high variability. Additionally, the materials being weighed in this cluster hold substantial value. However, given the use of European load cells and a lower volume of weightings compared to other clusters, calibration holds relatively less significance for this cluster. Nonetheless, it should not be disregarded.

Calibration importance is ranked lowest for the clusters of "Economic Truck Scales" and "Business Truck Scales." These scales, being situated within covered enclosures, do not perform a high volume of weightings throughout the day, and environmental conditions at their installation sites exhibit lower variability. Consequently, calibration holds relatively less significance for these clusters.

In conclusion, while this research has provided a ranking of the importance of calibration throughout the year for each cluster and business, it is crucial to emphasize that even the lowest-ranked clusters in this study are not exempt from calibration requirements. Calibration should be conducted regularly for these scales, albeit with a lower frequency and shorter calibration intervals compared to other clusters and higher-ranked categories.

Based on the results obtained and the analyses conducted on the clusters and customers utilizing roadside truck scales, the following recommendations are proposed:

- It is recommended to plan a higher frequency of calibration throughout the year for roadside scales. As mentioned earlier, even the lowest-ranked clusters in this study are not exempt from calibration requirements, and calibration should be

conducted regularly for these truck scales. However, the calibration frequency and intervals can be lower compared to other clusters and higher-ranked categories.

- It is advisable to plan the calibration intervals according to the importance of calibration for each cluster. Clusters that have achieved higher rankings in the calibration importance study should aim to reduce their calibration intervals as much as possible. Reducing the calibration interval not only enhances the accuracy and precision of roadside truck scales but also ensures the equipment's integrity and operational quality.
- Research efforts should be directed towards advertising planning in this domain. Considering the results regarding the significance of calibration for each cluster and the suggested minimum optimal calibration frequency for each scale, advertising campaigns can be structured in a way that encourages service companies to conduct calibration advertisements when businesses and industries are in need.
- Industries tend to use roadside truck scales more frequently during specific time intervals throughout the year. It is recommended to plan advertising campaigns based on these time intervals with the highest usage of scales for each industry.

Considering that the present research has examined data and calibration criteria for weighing equipment in the field of roadside truck scales, it is recommended to establish calibration criteria for other weighing equipment such as digital scales (Basculete), floor scales, and balances. Additionally, clustering of customers in these domains should be conducted to determine the optimal calibration frequency for these weighing instruments as well. It is worth noting that this research has focused on

industries and businesses using roadside truck scales, so its generalizability to all types of weighing equipment requiring calibration may be limited.

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